

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TEACHERS' WORKLOAD AND JOB SATISFACTION IN TIME OF PANDEMIC

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The Relationship Between Teachers' Workload and Job Satisfaction in Time of Pandemic

Maria Joan L. Caballes,* Lorelie V. Gamutan
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study aimed to determine the relationship between the teachers' job satisfaction and their workload in this time of pandemic. As educators, it is necessary to look into the factors related to teachers' job satisfaction that may affect their work performance. This study was limited to the one hundred teachers randomly chosen from Don Carlos 2 District. It focused on the teacher's workload in this pandemic which includes number of hours or period taught, the school organization handled and administrative role. It determined the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, position, civil status, family monthly income, highest educational attainment and years of teaching. It also determined the job satisfaction of the teachers in terms of compensation, work load, school head's support, personal growth and professional growth. The following descriptive statistics were used in this study: weighted mean and standard deviation, frequency count and percentage, Pearson r, and ANOVA. The following are the findings of this study: Demographic profile of teacher respondents majority are female teachers, married, occupying Teacher-1 position with a monthly income between 20,500- 24,999 in the department. The work assignment of the teachers respondents are the following: Teacher respondents were assigned in Grade 3. They print, staple and pack modules in eight (8) hours. Some of these teachers were assigned as Property Custodian of the school and some are assigned to ancillary services specifically on managing student services such as guidan. The current study revealed that as to the extent of teachers' job satisfaction in terms of compensation, work assignment, school head's support, personal growth, professional growth and work condition, the results showed that they are satisfied with their work assignment and work condition. However, they are only slightly satisfied with compensation, school head's support, personal and professional growth. It also showed that there is no significant relationship between demographic profile of the teachers and their job satisfaction during pandemic. Finally, there is no significant relationship between teachers' work assignment and their job satisfaction during pandemic.

Keywords: *teachers workload, job satisfaction, pandemic*

Introduction

The Covid-19 pandemic has had an impact on teachers' working conditions, including their hours, job satisfaction, and sources of pressure and support. What effects is the Covid-19 pandemic having on the professional lives of leaders and teachers? The Covid-19 pandemic has harmed many elements of life in society, not least among teachers and schools. Teachers' job happiness may be impacted by their increased workload.

The level of commitment and productivity within the school organization depends on employee happiness. The teachers' loyalty to the organization was significantly influenced by their job satisfaction. Teachers who enjoy their employment are more likely to stick around the business. Employers' participation and loyalty to the company increase as their job satisfaction increases (Shila et al., 2015). The entire effectiveness of the school is influenced by the instructors' contentment or satisfaction with the organization. This is because it affects how they carry out their jobs in general (Sadasa, 2015).

Job satisfaction affects student achievement, and without improvements in these two areas, education cannot grow. Every organization's ultimate purpose is to enhance schools, provide high-quality education, and make learning enjoyable for students. Additionally, this trait significantly affects leadership behavior, job performance, and leadership styles (Maqbool, 2017). In the workplace, it is essential. Job success, job motivation, and job adaptability may all be impacted by one another. Satisfaction, health security creditability, and compliance with essential criteria can all be obtained when performance is improved (Mirzaii et al., 2015).

Due to various changes brought on by the pandemic, teachers' typical skills are limited. This causes reduced levels of satisfaction and productivity as well as fatigue and tension. When teachers are under a lot of strain, their students perform poorly academically and socially, which manifests as tardiness, bad behavior, and unhappiness (Greenberg, MT et al.2016). Every teacher at every school in Southern Tulare County, California, has moderately high to high levels of job satisfaction. Increased student achievement, improved school atmosphere, teacher retention, and instructional performance are all directly correlated with teacher job satisfaction.

Due to the significant alteration of teachers' roles, there has been a shift to a heavier workload. As a result, job discontent negatively affects teachers' well-being and ability to cope. It is one of the things that instructors most frequently cite as having a significant impact on their capacity to complete their work (Cox, Solomon, & Parris, 2018). An educational system's functioning, effectiveness, and success are all correlated with teachers' health. As a result, addressing work-related stress should be a top priority and be done in conjunction with mental health promotion in order to improve the overall effectiveness of school.

An "unmanageable workload" is one of the main reasons teachers cite for leaving the public sector (Worth, 2020a). Teachers work

more hours per week than other professionals, albeit this is not the same as the actual number of hours worked. Teachers may experience a worse work-life balance, job discontent, and higher levels of stress if they work hard for fewer weeks out of the year. According to Worth and Van den Brande's 2019 research, 41% of teachers, compared to 32% of other professionals in a similar field, are dissatisfied with the quantity of free time they have. Additionally, 20% of teachers report feeling stressed about their jobs most of the time or always, compared to 13% of other professionals in similar fields.

As educators, it is important to consider the elements that may have an impact on teachers' job happiness. Therefore, the researcher is interested in establishing the connection between the workload of the instructors during this epidemic and their job happiness.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the level of job satisfaction of teachers in this time of COVID-19 pandemic. This study was guided with the following research questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the teachers in terms of age, gender, annual income, civil status and years in service?
2. What is the work assignment of the teachers during pandemic in terms of grade level taught, number of hours or periods taught, paper works and submissions, school organization handled and administrative role?
3. What is the extent of teachers' job satisfaction in terms of compensation, workload, school head's support, personal growth, professional growth and work condition?
4. Is there a significant relationship between demographic profile of the teachers and their job satisfaction during pandemic?
5. Is there a significant relationship between work assignment of the teachers and their job satisfaction during pandemic?

Methodology

Research Design

The descriptive correlational design was used in this investigation. The optimal research strategy for this study is descriptive correlational because the researcher will carefully investigate the data regarding the relationship between teacher workload and job satisfaction in this epidemic period.

The purpose of this study, which was to evaluate the workload of teachers and their job satisfaction in this time of pandemic, is best served by using a descriptive research design, which was utilized when a study focuses on the current situation and the goal is to discover new truth.

Respondents

The respondents were the one hundred elementary teachers randomly chosen who are from Don Carlos II District. Randomly chosen school head teachers from Don Carlos II District will also be chosen.

<i>Name of School</i>	<i>Number of Teachers</i>	<i>Sample Size</i>
Bismartz ES	13	13
Bochoc CES	16	16
Cabadiangan ES	6	6
Kalubihon ES	7	7
Kawilihan ES	9	9
Kiara ES	17	17
Mahayahay ES	8	8
Mauswagon ES	7	7
New Nongnongan ES	11	11
New Visayas ES	8	8
San Antonio ES	13	13
San Francisco ES	7	7
Sto. Niño ES	4	4
Total	126	126

The study will employ take all or complete remuneration sampling procedure choosing all the public school teachers and school heads in the research locale.

Instrument

The instrument was adapted but modified from the study conducted by Pamela Adhiambo Nyagaya entitled "factors influencing teachers' level of job satisfaction in public primary schools in kayole division, embakasi sub county, kenya".

It was pretested through a pilot study and the cronbach alpha value is 0.9453 which means that the validity and reliability of the instrument is high.

The questionnaires for both teachers and head teachers had both closed and open ended items which required the respondents to select

one response from given alternatives and open ended items which required the respondents to express their personal views about the questions asked. The questionnaires had sections. Section I had questions on the general demographic information of the respondents. Section II consisted of questions on influence of the various variables on teachers' level of job satisfaction in public primary schools. The interviews were used to get in depth information from the head teachers and the teachers about the teachers' level of job satisfaction and it will also assist to give more information on the same to the researcher.

Procedure

The researcher requested approval from Bukidnon's Office of the Schools Division Superintendent to carry out the study. The Don Carlos II District school heads were informed once permission was requested. The respondent instructors' permission was requested.

Given the epidemic at hand, minimal exposure was required, hence the researcher herself gave the questionnaire using Google Forms. By answering the questionnaire, respondents were assured of the confidentiality of the information acquired.

If there were any mistakes made when filling out the questionnaire, the researcher would email the respondents and ask them to clarify their responses. It would be taken out of this study if it was impossible to obtain clarifications. All results were digitally computed once respondents completed the survey's Google form. The study's data would only be accessible to the researcher. The data gathering forms were kept around till the study's end.

The questionnaire was delivered to participants with enough time to complete it. Participants' questions will only be addressed by the researcher himself. Only the participant's assigned number will be projected in the data form after the data have been encoded and compiled.

Data Analysis

To answer problems 1, the researcher will use frequency and percent count. To answer problems 2 use frequency count, percent, and mean. , For problem 3-4 the researcher will use the Pearson r correlation coefficient and for problem 5 use linear regression.

Results and Discussion

This chapter discusses the analysis and interpretation of the data gathered on the level of job satisfaction of teachers in this time of COVID-19 pandemic. The discussion is based on the problems to be investigated stated in Chapter 1.

Demographic profile of teachers in terms of age, gender, civil status, position, annual income, highest educational attainment, and length of service

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of teachers in terms of age, gender, civil status, position, annual income, highest educational attainment, and length of service.

Table 1. *Demographic Profile of Teachers in terms of Age, Gender, Civil status, Position, Annual Income, Highest Educational Attainment, and Length of Service*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Frequency Counts</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Age		
51 years old and above	8	7.92
40-50 years old	24	23.76
30-39 years old	44	43.56
20-29 years old	25	24.75
Total	101	100
Gender		
Male	26	25.74
Female	75	74.26
Total	101	100
Civil Status		
Single	37	36.63
Married	64	63.37
Separated	0	0
Widow	0	0
Widower	0	0
Total	101	100
Position		
Master Teacher IV	0	0
Master Teacher III	0	0
Master Teacher II	8	7.92
Master Teacher I	22	21.78
Teacher III	12	11.88
Teacher II	6	5.94

Teacher I	53	52.47
Total	101	100
Annual Income		
50,000 and above	4	3.96
40,000-49,999	19	18.81
35,000- 39,999	8	7.92
25,000-29,999	14	13.86
20,500-24,999	34	33.66
30,000-39,999	0	0
Total	101	100
Highest Educational attainment		
PhD Degree	40	39.60
MA Holder with PhD units	17	16.83
MA holder	27	26.73
College graduate with MA units	15	14.85
College graduate	2	1.98
Total	101	100
Length of Service		
21 years and above	12	11.88
16 years – 20 years	13	12.87
11 years -15 years	24	23.76
6 years- 10 years	30	29.70
5 years below	22	21.78
Total	101	100

Table 1 reveals the demographic profile of teachers. On age profile, 44 out of 101 teachers have ages that ranges from 30-39 which constitutes 43.56% of the sample. However, only 8 out of 101 age 50 years old and above. This means teachers of the district are still active, young and supportive to the mandates of the department. This also implies that in this pandemic where there is a shift into the traditional works of teachers, this age group are capable of doing their new tasks especially in blended learning. This is very important because of the new roles and tasks that teachers are facing this pandemic. It has been observed that with this pandemic, the younger the teachers are, the more likely they can cope with the new shift in the job especially in the use of technology as part of the teaching and learning process.

Work assignment of the teachers during pandemic in terms of grade level taught, number of hours spent in preparing the modules, coordinatorship, and ancillary services

Table 2 presents the work assignment of teachers during pandemic in terms of grade level taught, number of hours spent in preparing the modules, coordinator ship, and ancillary services.

Table 2. Work Assignment of Teachers in Terms of Grade Level Taught, Number of Hours Spent in Preparing the Modules, Coordinatorship, and Ancillary Services

<i>Grade Level Taught</i>	<i>Frequency Counts</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Kindergarten	14	13.86
1	13	12.87
2	15	14.85
3	17	16.83
4	14	13.86
5	14	13.86
6	14	13.86
Total	101	100.00
Number of Hours Spent in Preparing the Modules		
8 hours	101	100
6-7 hours	0	0
4-5 hours	0	0
2-3 hours	0	0
Total	101	100.00
Coordinatorship		
Feeding Coordinator	3	2.97
Sports Coordinator	4	3.96
Work Assignment		
Gulayan Coordinator	3	2.97
School Paper Adviser	4	3.96
Disaster Risk Reduction Management Coordinator	7	6.93
Phi-IRI Coordinator	11	10.89

School -Based Management Coordinator	10	9.9
Property Custodian	27	26.73
Supreme Pupil Government (SPG) Adviser	6	5.94
Scouting Coodinator	11	10.89
ICT Coordinator	15	14.85
Total	101	100.00
Ancillary Services		
Managing student services such as guidance programs	66	65.35
Managing budgets and ensuring financial systems	11	10.89
Purchasing goods and equipment	3	2.97
Liaising with partner/ other institutions, external agencies, government agencies	21	20.79

The data divulge the work assignment of teachers which are as follows; grade level taught, number of hours spent in preparing the modules, coordinatorship, and ancillary services. These work assignments are performed during pandemic. Although teachers do not practice actual or face to face teaching, they are still handling a section where they are incharge of distribution and retrieval of modules. On the grade level assignment ,16.83% of the teacher respondents are handling Grade 3 and few of them handles Grade 1 (12.87%).

Numerous studies that claimed that instructors' workloads and work assignments changed during the pandemic lend credence to this conclusion. The work patterns for teachers were significantly changed during the worldwide health crises (Sokal et al., 2020). These occupations had been well studied before the epidemic, and research found that there was a significant amount of job overload that led to burnout (Smetackova et al., 2019). In the educational field, teachers must manage their workload and set aside additional time to look after parents and guardians, prepare materials, and plan, most of which is done at home (Robalino et al., 2005). The country's education system is "under assault," just as the healthcare system is due to the increase in coronavirus disease (COVID-19) cases, as indicators of fatigue among educators' frontline staff endanger learning continuity (Smetackova et al., 2019)..

The amount of hours spent creating the modules is another task that the respondents completed. They spend their time printing, counting, and packing the modules. As a result, every respondent has this work finished and ready to distribute in the upcoming weeks and months. In addition to this, teachers are given additional tasks to complete in order for their school to accept coordinator or chairmen on the many DepEd programs and events. Being the school property custodian (26.73 percent) is the most additional duty given to teachers out of the eleven (11) programs/activities. Due to the epidemic, teachers are currently underutilized for two work assignments: Gulayan Coordinator and Supreme Student Government Adviser (9.54 percent).

If the teacher is not assigned from the aforementioned work assignments, they can be assigned to administrative roles to perform ancillary services. Managing student services such as guidance programs is the most prevalent services teachers offer (65.35%) and only 2.97% of the teachers accept the responsibility to purchasing goods and equipment .

The above results imply that the work of teachers in this pandemic even if there are no face to face classes is not easy. This is due to the fact that they need to spend eight hours or more to prepare the modules on top of the extra assignments handed to them. This finding is supported by a survey conducted by ACT from March to April 2020, which found that more than 70% of teacher respondents believe the workload associated with distance learning is "negatively impacting on their physical and mental health" - with about 10% admitting they have "already fallen ill due to the problems with distance learning and their burdensome duties." In the first half of the academic year (SY) 2020–2021, the survey seeks to "evaluate the work status of education frontliners" (<https://mb.com.ph/>).

Extent of teachers’ job satisfaction in terms of compensation, work assignment, school head’s support, personal growth ,professional growth and work condition

Table 3 presents the extent of teacher’s job satisfaction in terms of compensation.

Table 3. Extent of Teacher’s Job Satisfaction in Terms of Compensation

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
1. I am happy with my compensation regardless of my workload.	2.4554	0.7813	Slightly Satisfied
2. I am satisfied with my compensation	2.4851	0.7696	Slightly Satisfied
3. My compensation gives justice to my current workload	2.3861	0.8482	Slightly Satisfied
4. I am motivated to do good work because of my compensation	2.8614	0.8948	Satisfied
5. I feel that my compensation inspires me so much to work well.	2.3861	0.8482	Slightly Satisfied
Overall	2.5148	0.0424	Slightly Satisfied

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Extremely Satisfied | 3.40 – 4.19 Very Satisfied | 2.60 – 3.39 Satisfied | 1.80 – 2.59 Slightly Satisfied | 1.00 – 1.79 Not Satisfied

Table 3 reveals the job satisfaction of teachers in terms of compensation. It indicates that the indicator I am motivated to do good work because of my compensation (wt mean =2.8614, SD=0.8948) was the dominant response of the teachers described as satisfied. On the contrary, the indicators my compensation gives justice to my current workload (wt. mean=2.3861, SD=0.8482) and I feel that my compensation inspires me so much to work well were the least responses described as slightly satisfied. As a whole, job satisfaction of teachers is accounted for in the compensation they received (wt. mean=2.5148, SD=0.0424) described as slightly satisfied.

This implies that compensation is a big factor in the job satisfaction of teachers. Numerous studies back up this. A. Yaseen (2013) discovered that income, recognition, possibilities for advancement, and meaningful work are crucial aspects of compensation management that directly influence doctors' job satisfaction. The main causes of doctors' discontent are inadequate service structures and a lack of significance in their employment. By offering this kind of non-financial incentive to doctors, the government should raise their level of satisfaction. Likewise, Malik, et al. (2012) looked on how pay and promotions affected work satisfaction at Punjabi universities. The results show that while income has a big impact on job happiness, promotions have a significant or minor impact on educators' job satisfaction.

With the above result, it can be concluded that there must be an improvement in the compensation of teachers as they are only slightly satisfied with what they received in proportion of the workload and assignments they have. Authorities can take a look at it as basis to create laws to improve the salary of teachers.

Table 4 shows the extent of teacher's job satisfaction in terms of work assignment.

Table 4. Extent of Teacher's Job Satisfaction in Terms of Work Assignment

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
1. I am happy and contented with my workload.	2.7921	0.8980	Satisfied
2. My physical working conditions are reasonable for my type of work.	2.8416	0.8914	Satisfied
3. I have been provided with the workspace, equipment and tools I need to perform at my best	2.3861	0.8482	Slightly satisfied
4. I am always positive with my work despite my workload.	2.8911	0.9263	Satisfied
5. I strive hard be competent in my performance despite my workload	2.8416	0.891	Satisfied
Overall	2.7505	0.0171	Satisfied

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Extremely Satisfied | 3.40 – 4.19 Very Satisfied | 2.60 – 3.39 Satisfied | 1.80 – 2.59 Slightly Satisfied | 1.00 – 1.79 Not Satisfied

Table 4 reveals the job satisfaction of teachers in terms of work assignment. With a mean of 2.8911, the result shows that respondents are always positive with their work despite their workload. On the other hand, the lowest indicator is “I have been provided with the workspace, equipment and tools I need to perform at my best “ with a mean of 2.3861. Taken as a whole, with a mean of 2.7505, the study shows that the teachers are satisfied with their work assignment. It implies that the respondent teachers are not complaining with the work assignment that is assigned to them. This may have something to do with the age group of these respondents considering that majority of them are still young, active and engaging.

This finding runs counter to the other pieces of literature that discuss how unhappy instructors are with their workload. Teachers also mentioned heavy workloads, psychological issues, and weariness in a research done in Spain during the start of the pandemic (Prado-Gascó et al., 2020). Additionally, past research has shown that utilizing ICT while working from home can lead to emotions of stress, worry, weariness, and poor job satisfaction (Cuervo et al., 2018), yet in a pandemic these were the only resources available to instructors.

The teaching profession has always been stressful because of the nature of the work that teachers do, high workloads, issues with interpersonal communication, a lack of training, and job instability (Pérez, 2003). There have been several cases of stress, anxiety, and depression in the teaching profession, according to research done in several different nations (Ryan et al., 2017; Von der Embse et al., 2019). In fact, psychological symptomatology has been researched among university teachers, elementary school teachers, and secondary school teachers (Extremera et al., 2010; Skaalvik and Skaalvik, 2016; Abdullah and Ismail, 2019). (Malik et al., 2017; Puertas-Molero et al., 2018).

Table 5 shows the extent of teacher's job satisfaction in terms of School Head's Support.

Table 5. Extent of Teacher's Job Satisfaction in Terms of School Head's Support

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
1. I am happy and contented with how my school head supports us in this pandemic.	2.8614	0.9168	Satisfied
2. My School Head helps us manage our workload.	2.8317	0.8952	Satisfied
3. My School Head advices us about doing our best to excel in our work despite this pandemic.	2.3960	0.7359	Slightly Satisfied
4. I am satisfied with my school head's support in this pandemic.	2.3564	0.7821	Satisfied Slightly
5. I am satisfied with my school head's leadership in this pandemic.	2.4455	0.7678	Slightly Satisfied
Overall	2.578	0.0692	Slightly Satisfied

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Extremely Satisfied | 3.40 – 4.19 Very Satisfied | 2.60 – 3.39 Satisfied | 1.80 – 2.59 Slightly Satisfied | 1.00 – 1.79 Not Satisfied

Table 5 reveals the job satisfaction of teachers in terms of School Heads' support. With a mean of 2.8614, respondents agreed that they are happy and contented with how their school head supports them in this pandemic. On the other hand, only few of them were satisfied with their school head's support in this pandemic. This means that being happy and satisfied with the school head's support are two different things. Taken as a whole, with a mean of 2.578, the study shows that the teachers are slightly satisfied with their work School

heads' support. This implies that teachers are not really satisfied with the support they received from their School heads. This is a wakeup call because the support of school head is a significant factor in the performance of teachers. Sewell and Abel. (2015) found that the two main sources of stress for urban teachers were insufficient administrative assistance and a lack of praise for effective instruction. Teachers in urban schools are much more stressed than those in rural schools as a result of unfavorable working circumstances and strained staff relationships. It was discovered that key relationships exist between how school leaders support teacher recruitment, development, and retention. These relationships include teacher satisfaction, school performance, improvement, capacity, teacher leadership, distributive leadership, organizational learning, and development. School administrators can significantly influence these school-level factors while also serving as a check on the excesses of escalating and occasionally contradictory external pressures. As a result, ensuring that teachers are adequately overseen is one of the most crucial issues for the performance of educational institutions. As noted by Adu, Akinloye, and Olaoye (2014), supervision—whether internal or external—should be seen as a deliberate endeavor aimed at enhancing the outcomes of each educational institution. In order to enhance teaching and student success, it is a technique for including teachers in instructional dialogue (Sullivan & Glanz, 2013). Johnson, Kraft, and Papay (2012) looked into how working circumstances in schools affected teachers' intentions for their future careers and job satisfaction. According to the survey, the social aspects of teacher working conditions were the most significant of all the employed types. A school's culture of trust and respect, the leadership of the principal, and collegial support had an impact that was nearly twice as great as its material resources.

Table 6 presents the extent of teacher's job satisfaction in terms of Personal Growth.

Table 6. *Extent of Teacher's Job Satisfaction in Terms of Personal Growth*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
1. Additional workload during this pandemic did not affect my personal relationship with my family.	2.4851	0.7696	Slightly satisfied
2. I am happy and contented with my workload this pandemic because it helps me improve my personal relationship with my co teachers.	2.1782	0.7127	Slightly Satisfied
3. I am happy and contented with my workload this pandemic because it helps me improve my personal relationship with my School Head	2.2277	0.7195	Slightly Satisfied
4. I am happy and contented with my workload this pandemic because it helps me improve my personal relationship with my students.	2.2178	0.7156	Slightly Satisfied
5. I am happy and contented with my workload this pandemic because it helps me become a better teacher	2.8614	0.8948	Satisfied
Overall	2.3940	0.0559	Slightly Satisfied

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Extremely Satisfied | 3.40 – 4.19 Very Satisfied | 2.60 – 3.39 Satisfied | 1.80 – 2.59 Slightly Satisfied | 1.00 – 1.79 Not Satisfied

Table 6 reveals the job satisfaction of teachers in terms of personal growth. With a mean of 2.8614, respondents agree that they are happy and contented with their workload this pandemic because it helps them become a better teacher. On the other hand, with a mean of 2.1782, only few of the respondents said that they are happy and contented with their workload this pandemic because it helps them improve their personal relationship with their co teachers. Taken as a whole, with a mean of 2.3940, the study shows that the teachers are slightly satisfied with their personal growth. This connotes that teachers are still seeking for more personal growth in their profession. Getting organized, fixing difficulties, engaging kids, and caring about them are all important life skills for teachers. Teachers must develop particular life skills relating to their personal lives because their professional roles can be influenced by personal circumstances.

Previous research has established an important contribution of teacher motivational beliefs on job satisfaction, personal growth and retention plans. It emphasized how many factors contribute to the dissatisfaction of teachers in their personal growth brought by the nature of their profession. Research on determinants of teacher job satisfaction has found consistent mitigating effects of teacher self-efficacy beliefs on stressful school working environment internationally, e.g. in Spain, Norway and Canada (Betoret, 2009; Collie et al., 2012). Additionally, higher work satisfaction and less plans to leave the profession were connected to higher levels of teacher self-efficacy beliefs (Klassen & Chiu, 2010; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2014). Furthermore, Klassen and Chiu (2011) came to the conclusion that the impact of stressful working conditions on teacher occupational commitment was mitigated by teacher self-efficacy. Similar to this, Collie et al. (2012) found that when stressful working conditions are combined with a high level of teacher self-efficacy, they are perceived as challenges that can be overcome and do not negatively affect job satisfaction. The study examined the relationships between teacher stress, self-efficacy, and job satisfaction of Canadian teachers.

Table 7 presents the extent of teacher's job satisfaction in terms of Personal Growth.

Table 7 reveals the job satisfaction of teachers in terms of professional growth. With a mean of 2.4752 the highest indicator is "Additional workload during this pandemic helps me grow professionally" and the lowest indicator is "My workload this pandemic because it help me improve my time management" (mean=2.1881). Taken as a whole, with a mean of 2.2594, the study shows that the teachers are slightly satisfied with their professional growth. This may have something to do with how busy they are with their workload. Any form of continuous education effort for educators is referred to as teacher professional development. It's one way for educators to improve their abilities and, as a result, improve student outcomes. Planning and executing unique chances for instructors to continue to develop their skills is difficult. In the middle of a hectic school day, many school leaders will admit that professional

development is the last thing on their minds. Educators organize their professional development using self-assessment, current research, evidence, and lessons learned. Professional learning opportunities are designed with curriculum, training, and evaluation in mind, and participation in professional learning improves professional practice. The result implies that the teachers are still seeking more training and activities for their professional growth.

Table 7. *Extent of Teacher's Job Satisfaction in Terms of Professional Growth*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
1. My workload this pandemic helps me improve my skills	2.2277	0.7195	Slightly satisfied
2. My workload this pandemic helps me improve my leadership.	2.2079	0.7914	Slightly Satisfied
3. My workload this pandemic because it help me improve my time management.	2.1881	0.7030	Slightly Satisfied
4. Additional workload during this pandemic helps me grow professionally.	2.4752	0.7693	Slightly Satisfied
5. I believe that additional workload will hone teacher's knowledge and skills.	2.1980	0.7351	Satisfied
Overall	2.2594	0.0294	Slightly Satisfied

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Extremely Satisfied | 3.40 – 4.19 Very Satisfied | 2.60 – 3.39 Satisfied | 1.80 – 2.59 Slightly Satisfied | 1.00 – 1.79 Not Satisfied

High-quality professional development strategies are essential to schools. Effective professional development should help teachers learn how to use their limited time in an efficient and effective manner. Professional development transforms teachers into better and more apt educators by enabling them to create relevant and tailored course instructions for today's students. When educators discover new teaching strategies through professional development, they are able to go back to the classroom and make changes to their lecture styles and curricula to better suit the needs of their students.

Table 8 presents the extent of teacher's job satisfaction in terms of Work Condition

Table 8. *Extent of Teacher's Job Satisfaction in Terms of Work Condition*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
1. I am happy with my work regardless of my workload.	2.6040	0.9064	Satisfied
2. I understand how the work I do relates to the overall goals and priorities of the agency/department.	2.9307	0.9408	Satisfied
3. The tasks given to me are very helpful in my growth.	2.8614	0.8948	Satisfied
4. I am motivated to do good work.	2.5248	0.8555	Slightly Satisfied
5. I feel that I am as productive as I can be.	2.9109	0.9602	Satisfied
Overall	2.7664	0.0312	Satisfied

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Extremely Satisfied | 3.40 – 4.19 Very Satisfied | 2.60 – 3.39 Satisfied | 1.80 – 2.59 Slightly Satisfied | 1.00 – 1.79 Not Satisfied

Table 8 reveals the job satisfaction of teachers in terms of work condition. The highest indicator is "I understand how the work I do relates to the overall goals and priorities of the agency/department" (mean=2.9307). On the other hand, the lowest indicator is "I am motivated to do good work" (mean=2.5248). Taken as a whole, with a mean of 2.7664, the study shows that the teachers are satisfied with their work condition. This implies that teachers received and experienced good working conditions in their school.

Results demonstrate a substantial association between school working conditions and teacher job satisfaction. More specifically, teacher workload, teacher cooperation and teacher perceptions of student discipline in school were the factors most closely related to teacher job satisfaction (Tropova 2019).

Likewise, Bari, et al. al. (2013) discovered that employee attitude and performance in the workplace are positively impacted by freedom, career development plans, employee valuation, learning opportunities, an open and comfortable work environment, and strong supervisory relationships. They added that emphasizing the elements that have a favorable influence on employee attitudes and performance would improve employee performance and foster a happy work environment, both of which would help the institute and its productivity flourish.

According to international studies, earnings are merely a minor source of discontent for teachers, with the primary causes of turnover being the declining prestige of the teaching profession and an unsatisfactory work environment (Borman & Dowling, 2008; Ingersoll & Smith, 2004; TemaNord, 2010). Additionally, poor working conditions at a school degrade the standing of the profession and make it challenging to find new instructors (Ingersoll, 2001). However, as long as a significant portion of the newly hired teachers leave the classroom due to dissatisfaction with their professional standing and working conditions, even hiring additional teachers may not be able to address the issue of teacher turnover (Ingersoll, 2017; Sutchter, Darling-Hammond, & Carver-Thomas, 2016).

Additionally, Ronfeldt et al. (2013) pointed out that finding, hiring, and training new teachers comes at a large financial expense. These expenses consume money that could be used to improve the working conditions in schools, an essential measure in keeping talented instructors (Borman & Dowling, 2008). As a result, attempts to retain teachers are becoming more prominent in legislative approaches to address the teacher shortage (Ingersoll, 2017; Sibieta, 2018; Sutchter et al., 2016; Worth & De Lazzari, 2017). These initiatives are especially important for math and science teachers, who are more likely to leave the profession than other types of educators (Ingersoll & May, 2012; Sibieta, 2018).

Test for significant relationship between demographic profile of the teachers and their job satisfaction during pandemic

Table 9 shows the test for significant relationship between demographic profile of teachers and their job satisfaction during pandemic.

Table 9. *Test for Significant Relationship between Demographic Profile of the Teachers and their Job Satisfaction on Compensation*

<i>Demographic Profile</i>	<i>Correlation Coefficient</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Age	-0.048	0.635	Not Significant
Gender	0.071	0.481	Not Significant
Civil Status	-0.147	0.143	Not Significant
Position	-0.034	0.739	Not Significant
Annual Income	-0.091	0.363	Not Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	-0.023	0.816	Not Significant
Length of Service	0.040	0.690	Not Significant

Level of Significance: $\alpha = 0.05$, $N = 101$

Table 9 exposes the result of the Pearson Correlation test to determine whether a significant relationship occur between the two variables, demographic profile of teachers and their job satisfaction on compensation. As shown, the p-values of each variable; age ($r = -0.048, p\text{-value} = 0.635$), gender ($r = 0.071, p\text{-value} = 0.491$), civil status ($r = -0.147, p\text{-value} = 0.143$), position ($r = -0.034, p\text{-value} = 0.739$), annual income ($r = -0.091, p\text{-value} = 0.363$), (highest educational attainment ($r = -0.023, p\text{-value} = 0.816$), (length of service ($r = 0.040, p\text{-value} = 0.690$) is greater than the level of significance which is set at $\alpha = 0.05$. Hence, the null hypothesis, there is no significant relationship between the demographic profile of teachers and their job satisfaction on compensation is not rejected. Therefore, there is no significant relationship between the demographic profile of teachers and their job satisfaction on compensation. This implies that the demographic profile of teachers does not affect their job satisfaction on compensation. It is contrary to most of the observations

This is contrary to the studies which show that demographic profile of a person is significant in their level of compensation satisfaction. According to GNAT, the pay problems facing some teachers across the country have dampened their spirits and its concomitant negative effect on the work output cannot be ignored. Their satisfaction on compensation is affected by age, their family income and number of family members. (www.ghanateachers.org/news, 2009).

Table 10 shows the test for significant relationship between demographic profile of teachers and their job satisfaction during pandemic.

Table 10. *Test for Significant Relationship between Demographic Profile of the Teachers and their Job Satisfaction on Work Assignment*

<i>Demographic Profile</i>	<i>Correlation Coefficient</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Age	0.0192	0.054	Not Significant
Gender	0.092	0.365	Not Significant
Civil Status	-0.082	0.413	Not Significant
Position	-0.114	0.256	Not Significant
Annual Income	-0.105	0.294	Not Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	-0.110	0.274	Not Significant
Length of Service	-0.131	0.193	Not Significant

Level of Significance: $\alpha = 0.05$, $N = 101$

Table 10 exposes the result of the Pearson Correlation test to determine whether a significant relationship occur between the two variables, demographic profile of teachers and their job satisfaction on work assignment. Taken as whole, the result shows that there is no significant relationship between the demographic profile of teachers and their job satisfaction on work assignment.

This is contrary to the studies which show that demographic profile of a person is significant in their level of work assignment satisfaction. According to Ahmadi & Alireza, 2007, how teachers look at their work assignment varies depending on their demographic profile. Job dissatisfaction, in contrast, can be due to an absence of work-life balance, a lack of advancement and opportunities, a non-supportive working environment, lack of encouragement, lack of recognition and stress which are all affected by demographic profiles of the teachers. These factors also increase the employee turnover rate (Ahmadi & Alireza, 2007). As a result, dissatisfied employees may reduce their levels of performance and efficiency and may sabotage the work or leave the job (Sonmezer & Eryaman, 2008). Dissatisfied employees leave the organisation and may deflate other employees' motivation before they do (Feinstein & Vondrasek, 2001).

Table 11 shows the test for significant relationship between demographic profile of teachers and their job satisfaction on school head's support during pandemic.

Table 11 exposes the result of the Pearson Correlation test to determine whether a significant relationship occur between the two variables, demographic profile of teachers and their job satisfaction on School heads' support. Taken as whole, the result shows that there is no significant relationship between the demographic profile of teachers and their job satisfaction on School heads' support.

It has been observed that regardless of the profile of the teachers, all really need good, positive and consistent School head support to effectively perform the task handed to them.

Table 11. *Test for Significant Relationship between Demographic Profile of the Teachers and their Job Satisfaction on School Head's Support*

Demographic Profile	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Remarks
Age	0.146	0.144	Not Significant
Gender	0.166	0.099	Not Significant
Civil Status	-0.206	0.039	Significant
Position	0.125	0.213	Not Significant
Annual Income	0.138	0.169	Not Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	-0.029	0.771	Not Significant
Length of Service	0.092	0.361	Not Significant

Level of Significance: $\alpha = 0.05$, $N = 101$

The data disclose that since all the p-values are greater than the level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$, there is no sufficient evidence at $\alpha = 0.05$ that the correlations are not zero, in part reflecting the large sample size of 101. However, the demographic profile on civil status has a p-value of 0.039 which is less than the level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$ where there is sufficient evidence that the correlation coefficient is not zero, therefore civil status is related with the job satisfaction of teachers on school head's support. In as much as out of seven (7) independent variable only one is significant, hence, the hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the demographic profile and the job satisfaction of teachers on school head's support is not rejected.

Table 12 shows the test for significant relationship between demographic profile of teachers and their job satisfaction on personal growth support during pandemic

Table 12. *Test for Significant Relationship between Demographic Profile of the Teach and their Job Satisfaction on Personal Growth*

Demographic Profile	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Remarks
Age	-0.144	0.151	Not Significant
Gender	0.107	0.290	Not Significant
Civil Status	0.180	0.072	Not Significant
Position	-0.090	0.373	Not Significant
Annual Income	-0.062	0.540	Not Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	-0.057	0.572	Not Significant
Length of Service	-0.005	0.962	Not Significant

Level of Significance: $\alpha = 0.05$, $N = 101$

Table 12 shows the result of the Pearson Correlation test to determine whether a significant relationship occur between the two variables, demographic profile of teachers and their job satisfaction on personal growth. Taken as whole, the result shows that there is no significant relationship between the demographic profile of teachers and their job satisfaction on personal growth.

It has been observed that regardless of the profile of the teachers, all really need the best personal growth they can acquire in the school to effectively perform the task handed to them.

Table 13 shows the test for significant relationship between demographic profile of teachers and their job satisfaction on professional growth support during pandemic.

Table 13. *Test for Significant Relationship between Demographic Profile of the Teachers and their Job Satisfaction on Professional Growth*

Demographic Profile	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Remarks
Age	-0.110	0.273	Not Significant
Gender	0.147	0.145	Not Significant
Civil Status	0.035	0.730	Not Significant
Position	0.082	0.416	Not Significant
Annual Income	-0.068	0.498	Not Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	-0.100	0.321	Not Significant
Length of Service	0.000	0.998	Not Significant

Level of Significance: $\alpha = 0.05$, $N = 101$

Taken as whole, the result shows that there is no significant relationship between the demographic profile of teachers and their job satisfaction on professional growth. This implies that how teachers see and feel about the personal growth that the teaching profession brings is not affected by their age, highest educational attainment and occupation. This is contrary to the study which links the personal and professional demographic characteristics of teachers to their job satisfaction (Alshammari et al., 2018).

Table 14 shows the test for significant relationship between demographic profile of teachers and their job satisfaction on work condition support during pandemic.

Taken as whole, the result shows that there is no significant relationship between the demographic profile of teachers and their job satisfaction on work condition.

This implies that the job satisfaction on work condition of teachers is not affected by their age, highest educational attainment and occupation. Therefore, embracing and getting use to the work condition in a job is something personal to them and their perception varies regardless of their profile.

Table 14. *Test for Significant Relationship between Demographic Profile of the Teachers and their Job Satisfaction on Work Condition*

<i>Demographic Profile</i>	<i>Correlation Coefficient</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Age	-0.143	0.153	Not Significant
Gender	0.160	0.112	Not Significant
Civil Status	-0.086	0.392	Not Significant
Position	-0.042	0.676	Not Significant
Annual Income	-0.016	0.876	Not Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	-0.037	0.712	Not Significant
Length of Service	-0.065	0.516	Not Significant

Level of Significance: $\alpha = 0.05$, $N = 101$

Test for significant relationship between work assignment of the teachers and their job satisfaction during pandemic.

Table 15 presents the test for significant relationship between work assignment of teachers and their job satisfaction on compensation. and their Job Satisfaction on Compensation.

Table 15.

<i>Work Assignment</i>	<i>Correlation Coefficient</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Grade Level Assignment	-0.140	0.164	Not Significant
Reproduction of Modules	0.142	0.157	Not Significant
Coordinatorship	-0.030	0.765	Not Significant
Ancillary Services	0.036	0.718	Not Significant

Level of Significance: $\alpha = 0.05$, $N = 101$

Taken as a whole, the result shows that there is no significant relationship between work assignment of teachers and their job satisfaction on compensation. This implies that the different work assignment of teachers does not affect how they are satisfied with their job in terms of compensation.

This runs counter to research that claim instructors relate job happiness to their workload and pay. According to a number of studies (Adeoye & Fields (2015), Greene (2015), Gupta & Shaw (2015), salary and job satisfaction are closely related. Although secondary school teachers have greater psychological symptomatology than primary school teachers (Arias et al., 2019), other factors including remuneration, interactions with pupils, and relationships with peers are also significant determinants (Prieto and Bermejo, 2006). Teachers may experience health problems as a result of this stress, which could result in an increase in absences, sick days, and subpar job output (Moreno et al., 2004). Employee work satisfaction was found to be impacted by compensation and benefits in a 2016 study by the Society for Human Resource Management. According to the poll results, one of the top three factors that employees value most in a job is remuneration.

Table 16 presents the test for significant relationship between work assignment of teachers and their job satisfaction on Work Assignment

Table 16. *Test for Significant Relationship between Work Assignment of Teachers and their Job Satisfaction on Work Assignment*

<i>Work Assignment</i>	<i>Correlation Coefficient</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Grade Level Assignment	-0.162	0.104	Not Significant
Reproduction of Modules	0.189	0.058	Not Significant
Coordinatorship	-0.160	0.109	Not Significant
Ancillary Services	0.153	0.127	Not Significant

Level of Significance: $\alpha = 0.05$, $N = 101$

Taken as a whole, the result shows that there is no significant relationship between work assignment of teachers and their job satisfaction on work assignment.

This implies that the different work assignment of teachers does not affect how they are satisfied with their job in terms of work assignment.

Demirel (2014) asserts that there is a strong correlation between instructors' levels of job satisfaction and their contentment with their work assignments. Similarly, a meta-analysis study found a link between emotional weariness and job satisfaction that was unfavorable (Yorulmaz et al., 2017). As a result, it is seen that research on teachers' psychological health is primarily linked to contexts of denial, including stress and weariness brought on by their job (Spilt et al., 2011).

Table 17 presents the test for significant relationship between work assignment of teachers and their job satisfaction on school head's support..

Table 17. *Test for Significant Relationship between Work Assignment of Teachers and their Job Satisfaction on School Head's Support*

<i>Work Assignment</i>	<i>Correlation Coefficient</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Grade Level Assignment	0.092	0.360	Not Significant
Reproduction of Modules	0.024	0.812	Not Significant
Coordinatorship	-0.018	0.857	Not Significant
Ancillary Services	-0.201	0.044	Significant

Level of Significance: $\alpha=0.05$, $N=101$

The data disclose that all the p-values are greater than the level of significance $\alpha=0.05$, this means that there is no sufficient evidence that the correlation coefficient is not equal to zero. Therefore, there is no significant relationship between the work assignment of teachers and their job satisfaction on school Head's support. However, the work assignment on ancillary services or additional work assigned to a teacher is related to the school head's support ($r= -0.201$ $p\text{-value}=0.044$). Out of four (4) independent variables, only ancillary services is related to the school head's support hence, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the work assignment of teachers and their job satisfaction on school head's support is not rejected.

Table 18 presents the test for significant relationship between work assignment of teachers and their job satisfaction on Personal Growth.

Table 18. *Test for Significant Relationship between Work Assignment of Teachers and their Job Satisfaction on Personal Growth*

<i>Work Assignment</i>	<i>Correlation Coefficient</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Grade Level Assignment	0.083	0.407	Not Significant
Reproduction of Modules	0.009	0.925	Not Significant
Coordinatorship	-0.083	0.412	Not Significant
Ancillary Services	0.001	0.990	Not Significant

Level of Significance: $\alpha=0.05$, $N=101$

The result shows that there is no significant relationship between work assignments of teachers and their job satisfaction on personal growth.

It implies that the work assignment of teachers does not affect their job satisfaction on personal growth. It has been observed that personal growth vary depending on the perspective and experience of teachers, therefore there is no size fits all kind of professional growth in the teaching profession. Teachers must look at their situation in a positive side so that they can discover their own personal growth in their profession.

Table 19 presents the test for significant relationship between work assignment of teachers and their job satisfaction on Professional Growth

Table 19. *Test for Significant Relationship between Work Assignment of Teachers and their Job Satisfaction on Professional Growth*

<i>Work Assignment</i>	<i>Correlation Coefficient</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Grade Level Assignment	-0.020	0.840	Not Significant
Reproduction of Modules	0.100	0.318	Not Significant
Coordinatorship	-0.060	0.553	Not Significant
Ancillary Services	0.024	0.815	Not Significant

Level of Significance: $\alpha=0.05$, $N=101$

The result shows that there is no significant relationship between work assignments of teachers and their job satisfaction on professional growth.

It implies that the work assignment of teachers does not affect their job satisfaction on professional growth. Collaboration in teaching to attain professional growth is very important. Collaboration in teaching can take various forms, such as peer discourse or dialogue, seminars or workshops, observing colleagues' classroom teaching, action research in group or even informal communication like discussion, chat and other collective activities among colleagues.

Table 20 presents the test for significant relationship between work assignment of teachers and their job satisfaction on Work Condition.

Table 20. *Test for Significant Relationship between Work Assignment of Teachers and their Job Satisfaction on Work Condition*

<i>Work Assignment</i>	<i>Correlation Coefficient</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Grade Level Assignment	-0.132	0.189	Not Significant
Reproduction of Modules	0.097	0.334	Not Significant
Coordinatorship	-0.145	0.147	Not Significant
Ancillary Services	0.077	0.445	Not Significant

Level of Significance: $\alpha=0.05$, $N=101$

The result shows that there is no significant relationship between work assignment of teachers and their job satisfaction on Work

Condition. It implies that the work assignment of teachers does not affect their job satisfaction on work condition.

As was stressed, evidence from international studies reveals that teacher turnover is mostly caused by the declining status of the teaching profession and an unsatisfactory work environment, with salary being only a small source of unhappiness (Borman & Dowling, 2008; Ingersoll & Smith, 2004; TemaNord, 2010). Additionally, poor working conditions at a school degrade the standing of the profession and make it challenging to find new instructors (Ingersoll, 2001). However, as long as a significant portion of the newly hired teachers leave the classroom due to dissatisfaction with their professional standing and working conditions, even hiring additional teachers may not be able to address the issue of teacher turnover (Ingersoll, 2017; Sutchter, Darling-Hammond, & Carver-Thomas, 2016).

Conclusions

The result of this study showed that most of the teachers nowadays are still young and are active especially in the tasks given to them.

In addition, the teachers have many work assignment despite the fact that there is no face to face classes with this pandemic.

The work assignments of teachers cover not only on actual teaching but covers new task in this pandemic like preparing, distributing and retrieval of modules. This is an additional task on top of the other ancillary roles of teachers.

The respondents are still satisfied with their work assignments and work condition because they believe that this can help them in their teaching profession although it did not perfectly contributed to their personal growth. However, they are only slightly satisfied with their compensation, school head's support, personal growth, and professional growth. Similarly, they are slightly satisfied with their compensation, school head's support, personal and professional growth. This means authority must look at this to consider improving the compensation of teachers and to inform the School Heads to improve the support they are giving to the teachers.

The demographic profile of the teachers does not affect their job satisfaction except on the civil status which related to their job satisfaction on school head's support.

Finally, teachers' work assignment does not affect their job satisfaction during pandemic. Nevertheless, teacher's ancillary services is related to school head's support. Therefore, teachers are still satisfied with their job in this pandemic despite additional workload.

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following are recommended.

Government officers and Department of Education must reconsider creating laws to improve the compensation of the teachers especially that most of them are still young and are always looking forward to improve their living for greater opportunity while they are still young;

Department of Education must reconsider reevaluating the work assignments of the teachers whether it is too much or does it helps promote their personal growth and welfare. If not, then authorities must reduce the work assignment of the teachers focusing only the most important tasks necessary for the teaching process.

This means Government officers and Department of Education must consider improving the compensation of teachers and to inform the School Heads to improve the support they are giving to the teachers. School heads must evaluate the quality of support they are giving to their teachers especially in this time of pandemic;

Department of Education must also provide trainings and seminars to the teachers to teach them on how to improve their satisfaction on their job despite how tedious the job of the teacher is. However, schools must also provide enough support to teachers to aid them in their additional task especially on ancillary services or role they provide.

Finally, further studies with increased sample size shall be conducted to achieve more accurate and large results.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Maria Joan L. Caballes

Mahayahay Elementary School
Department of Education – Philippines

Lorelie V. Gamutan, PhD.

Valencia Colleges (Bukidnon), Inc. – Philippines